

EARLY KIDNEY FUNCTION MARKERS IN PRETERM INFANTS

¹Akhmedova D.I., ²Murtalibova N.M.

¹Tashkent Medical Pediatric Institute

²National Children's Medical Center

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Purpose of the study: to study kidney function in premature newborns comparing eGFR according to Cystatin C (CsC) and Creatinine (Cr) and their correlating with kidney size.

Material and methods. The study group consisted of 106 newborns born prematurely and control group consisted of 40 term neonates. Serum Cr and CsC levels assessed during the first week of life. A renal study performed to estimate renal size, with TKV calculation.

Research results. Prematurity negatively affects the development of renal tissue in newborns, even with the nominal end of nephrogenesis at 36 weeks of gestation. Cystatin C is a reliable marker that allows one to estimate GFR in preterm infants with ELBW and VLBW with a sensitivity of 89.5% and 86.7% with a specificity of 88.7% and 82.4%, respectively

Preterm infants pose significant challenges in assessing their kidney function and potential implications for later adult health. The reason for decreased nephron mass in preterm infants is that nephrogenesis is active until 36 weeks of pregnancy, and premature birth results in a loss of total nephron number. Additionally, preterm infants have a higher susceptibility to acute kidney injury (AKI), which can lead to nephron loss after birth. Preterm infants account for more than 80% of AKI cases in infancy, and there is a lack of established protocols for early recognition and follow-up.[1,2] Traditionally, acute kidney dysfunction has been determined solely by serum creatinine levels, which might not be suitable for preterm infants due to their low muscle mass.[3] Cystatin C, on the other hand, is a protein that is independent of muscle mass and has been suggested as a more reliable marker for glomerular filtration rate (GFR) in infants.[4]

Purpose of the study – to gather data on Cystatin C, creatinine, and renal mass in preterm and term infants in their first week of life to establish baseline data and compare the effectiveness of creatinine versus Cystatin C in defining AKI in preterm infants.

Material and methods. The clinical observations for the prospective study were conducted at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Center of Pediatrics and the National Children's Medical Center during the period of 2021–2022. The main group of the study comprised 106 newborns who were born prematurely, including 54 boys and 52 girls, resulting in an equal gender ratio within the group. Due to this gender balance, the subsequent study did not segregate subgroups based on gender.

The main group was further divided into three subgroups based on gestational age (GA):

- Group I: Consisted of 28 children of both sexes with a gestational age ranging from 28 weeks (weight 900g) to 31 weeks (weight 1500g). The average age was 29.86 ± 0.85 weeks, and the average weight was 1287.4 ± 138.7 g, categorizing them as Extremely Low Birth Weight (ELBW) and Very Low Birth Weight (VLBW) infants.
- Group II: Included 37 children of both sexes with a gestational age from 32 weeks (1600g) to 33 weeks (weight 2000g). The average age was 32.69 ± 0.18 weeks, with an average weight of 1859.6 ± 146.3 g, classifying them as Low Birth Weight (LBW) infants.

- Group III: Comprised 41 children of both sexes with a gestational age ranging from 34 weeks (weight 2100g) to 35 weeks (weight 2500g). The average age was 34.58 ± 0.19 weeks, and the average weight was 2286.3 ± 162.4 g, falling within the category of Near-Moderate Term (NMT) infants.

To enable statistical comparisons of the collected data for the study children, a control group (CG) of 40 healthy full-term children (with a gestational period of 40 weeks) was formed. The average age of the control group was 40.12 ± 0.17 weeks, with an average weight of 3248.4 ± 367.6 g.

Various research methods, including clinical, anthropometric, laboratory, and instrumental approaches, were employed in the study, with the results meticulously analyzed using statistical methods, particularly variation statistics, through Microsoft Office Excel-2019. These rigorous methodologies aimed to provide comprehensive insights into the health and development of premature infants across different gestational age groups compared to full-term infants.

Research results. Body weight at birth was recorded as 1287 ± 126 g in group I, 1859 ± 214 g in group II, and 2286 ± 186 g in group III, with a statistically significant difference noted ($p < 0.05$). The percentage decrease in body weight during the first week of life was 10.93% in group I, 5.69% in group II, and 3.31% in group III, although this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1. Dynamics of body weight of the studied children

Indicators	CG	Group I	II group	III group
Apgar score at 1 minute	9.0 ± 0.9	5.6 ± 1	6.3 ± 0.6	7.2 ± 0.8
Apgar score at 5 minutes	9.1 ± 0.7	6.2 ± 0.6	7.1 ± 0.7	7.0 ± 0.8
Average height of newborns, cm	52.1 ± 5.6	42.6 ± 4.2	46.6 ± 4.8	48.1 ± 5.7
Body weight at birth, g.	3248 ± 381	1287 ± 126	1859 ± 214	2286 ± 186
Loss of body weight in 2 days	28.5 ± 3.4	14 ± 1.6	18.9 ± 1.5	25.5 ± 2.2
Weight loss over 2 days, %	0.88%	1.09%	1.02%	1.12%
Loss of body weight over 7 days	58.4 ± 5.2	140.7 ± 13.6	105.7 ± 9.5	75.6 ± 7.8
Weight loss over 7 days, %	1.80%	10.93%	5.69%	3.31%
Body weight on day 8, g.	3152 ± 380	1127 ± 127	1653 ± 204	2045 ± 177

Studies conducted on children in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) revealed that the majority of children in groups II and III exhibited class II severity of the condition, while in group I, most children showed class III severity. This indicates that children in group I required more intensive therapeutic and resuscitative measures, such as mechanical ventilation and hemodynamic support, along with continuous monitoring of vital functions.

The assessment of respiratory dysfunction using the Silverman scale indicated that mild respiratory failure was predominant in groups II and III, whereas severe respiratory failure was more common in group I.

Newborns in group I were found to have spent a longer duration on mechanical ventilation (8.93 ± 2.85 days) compared to group III (4.71 ± 1.25 days), which is considered a risk factor for bronchopulmonary dysplasia and AKI. The duration of mechanical ventilation in Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (CPAP) mode was longer in group I due to greater alveolar and surfactant immaturity, necessitating positive pressure in the respiratory system.

Early neonatal pneumonia was significantly more frequent in group I compared to groups II and III. Support for the cardiovascular system (CVS) involved inotropic therapy and vasopressor drugs in children with Very Low Birth Weight (VLBW) and Extremely Low Birth

Weight (ELBW). The duration of inotropic treatment was similar between group I and group III, indicating uniformity in CVS disorders among premature infants.

Heart failure of grades II-III predominated in group I, while grades I-II were more commonly diagnosed in groups II and III according to the Kirklin classification. No significant differences were observed in the general blood test parameters, including hemoglobin and ESR, compared to the control group. The biochemical blood parameters of patients in the study groups showed statistically significant differences compared to the control group across various indicators. The differences were significant at levels ranging from $p < 0.05$ to $p < 0.001$.

In all study groups, indicators such as urea and albumin demonstrated significant differences from the CG at the level of $p < 0.001$. The group with the most significant variances from the CG was group I, particularly in indicators such as AST, ALT, urea, calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), creatinine, and albumin (all at $p < 0.001$).

In group II, the most statistically significant differences from the CG were observed in indicators including urea, bilirubin, creatinine, and albumin (all at $p < 0.001$), as well as ALT ($p < 0.05$).

In group III, the most significant variations from the CG were noted in AST, urea, bilirubin ($p < 0.001$), potassium (K), and albumin ($p < 0.01$), as well as glucose and phosphorus ($p < 0.05$). These findings highlight substantial biochemical differences in blood parameters among the study groups compared to the control group, indicating significant variations in metabolic and renal function.

The comparative analysis of excretory function indicators in patients from the study groups revealed significant differences compared to the control group (CG) in various parameters. Across all groups, there were notable variations from the CG in uric acid levels, Cystatin C (CsC), and Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) according to Creatinine (Cr) based on the Schwartz formula, all at a significance level of $p < 0.001$.

In groups I and II, there was a significant increase in creatinine (Cr) levels compared to the CG, with values of 43 ± 4 and 35.6 ± 3.9 , respectively, as opposed to 29.2 ± 3.6 ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, in group II, a significant difference from the CG was observed in GFR according to the Hoek formula at the level of $p < 0.001$, while in group III, this difference was significant at the level of $p < 0.01$. The rate of diuresis in patients from the study groups also significantly differed from the CG, with levels I and II at $p < 0.001$ and group III at $p < 0.05$.

Cystatin C (CsC) was identified as a dependable marker of GFR in premature newborns with Extremely Low Birth Weight (ELBW) and Very Low Birth Weight (VLBW), exhibiting a sensitivity of 89.5% and 86.7% with a specificity of 88.7% and 82.4%, respectively. When combined with assessments of kidney volume (specificity 88.62% and sensitivity 83.24%), CsC allows for a comprehensive evaluation of renal function in this patient population.

It's worth noting that only the levels of creatinine in group III and GFR according to CsC using the Hoek formula in group I did not show statistically significant differences. These findings underscore the importance of monitoring various excretory function indicators in premature infants to assess renal function accurately. (Table 2)

Table 2. Indicators of renal excretory function in the studied children (M±δ).

Indicators	KG	Group I	II group	III group
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Urea, mmol/l	6.4±0.6	7.6±0.8***	7.5±0.7***	7.4±0.8***
Creatinine (Cr), µmol/l	29.2±3.6	43±4***	35.6±3.9***	29.9±3.2
GFR by (Cr) by Schwartz, ml/min/m ²	42.2±5	22.7±2.9***	26.2±2.9***	31.6±3.5***
CsS, mg/l	1.52±0.14	2.27±0.24***	1.99±0.16***	1.84±0.16***
GFR according to (CsC), by Hoek, ml/min/m ²	60.9±6.6	58.5±7.1	55.2±6.9***	58±5.2**
Diuresis rate ml/kg/hour	3.54±0.33	4.3±0.37***	3.97±0.47***	3.7±0.31*
CsC, mg/l on days 5-6	1.59±0.15	2.25±0.19***	1.92±0.21***	1.78±0.17***
GFR ml/min/m ² for 5-6 days	60.7±5.6	58.5±7.1	55.3±5.1***	58.1±4.6*
CysC, mg/l on day 10	1.47±0.16	2.31±0.21***	1.99±0.22***	1.82±0.23***
GFR ml/min/m ² on the 10th day	60.4±6.6	58.5±4.8	55.2±4.1***	58.1±6.8*
CysC, mg/l on day 14	1.58±0.14	2.24±0.2***	2.01±0.17***	1.75±0.17***
GFR ml/min/m ² on the 14th day	61±5.6	58.5±5.1	55.3±5.7***	58.1±5.9**

Note: *-P<0.05, **-P<0.01, ***-P<0.001 – statistical significance in relation to the CG. GFR from day 5 was calculated by CysC, using the Hoek formula ml/min/m².

The results of the study indicate that the average Creatinine (Cr) levels at birth in groups I and II were found to be statistically significantly higher than their corresponding normal gestational age values, suggesting pathological changes in excretory function. Specifically, in group I, the Cr levels were significantly lower (p <0.05), likely due to the functional immaturity of the kidneys and the severity of the conditions present in these infants. The urinary output rate was comparable across all groups.

The initial urination of the newborns occurred, on average, after 17.28±1.27 hours of birth and was approximately 1.05±0.04 ml/kg/hour in the early stages of life. By days 6-7, the daily urinary output decreased to 1.47±0.08 ml/kg/hour. In cases where newborns were born to mothers with preeclampsia, the first urination occurred in the delivery room for 4 out of 7 cases, with subsequent urination taking place around 19.04±1.27 hours later. Daily diuresis within the first 7 days of life ranged from 0.48±0.06 to 0.97±0.07 ml/kg/hour for these infants, with some cases exhibiting low GFR and oliguria on days 3-4.

Across all studied groups, Cr and urea levels were significantly higher in the early neonatal period compared to the CG (Cr 29.2±3.6 µmol/l, urea 6.4±0.6 mmol/l). By the 10th day, a percentage of premature newborns in group I (45%) and group II (20%) still displayed swelling of the head and legs alongside decreased diuresis, potentially indicating respiratory-metabolic acidosis, hyponatremia, and hyperkalemia-related issues, leading to symptoms like agitation, regurgitation, convulsions, and decreased reflexes in some cases.

There was also a significant inverse correlation between the weight of premature newborns and urine osmolarity in the first week of life, as well as between birth weight and urine osmolarity. Additionally, chronic renal failure and preeclampsia in mothers were identified as significant risk factors for azotemia due to their impact on the nitrogen and water excretion functions of the kidneys.

Furthermore, hypoperfusion was strongly correlated with GFR by Cr, with GFR by CsC exhibiting weak negative correlations with birth weight and gestational age. Mean blood pressure was found to be more prognostically significant than diastolic blood pressure.

Ultrasound examinations of the kidneys in the control group showed fetal lobulation and kidney sizes within the age norms, indicating no abnormalities based on embryonic development features.

Table 3. Kidney size of the studied children on ultrasound (M±δ).

Indicators	KG	Group I	II group	III group
Left kidney				
Length, mm	38.6±4	32.5±3.5***	34.5±3.1***	36.9±3.5*
Width, mm	19.8±2	17.2±3.6***	17.9±1.9***	18.6±2.3**
Depth, mm	22.4±2.5	20.2±2.5**	21.1±2.2*	21.8±2
Volume, cm ³	8.92±1.5	5.83±1.46***	6.81±1.13***	7.82±1.47**
Chamber of Commerce and Industry, mm	7.83±0.78	6.75±0.75***	7.05±0.74***	7.56±0.71
Right kidney				
Length, mm	37.7±4.4	32.8±2.7***	34.6±3.3***	36.8±4.1
Width, mm	18.1±1.7	17±1.7**	17.3±1.5*	17.8±1.6
Depth, mm	25.8±2.8	22.1±2.4***	22.4±2***	24.9±2.6
Volume, cm ³	9.2±1.57	6.45±1.1***	6.99±0.99***	8.54±1.49*
Chamber of Commerce and Industry, mm	7.43±0.84	6.46±0.64***	6.95±0.7**	7.12±0.68*
Combined kidney volume cm ³	18.2±2	12.4±1.9***	13.8±1.8***	16.4±1.6***

Note: *-P<0.05, **-P<0.01, ***-P<0.001 – statistical significance in relation to the CG.

Specifically, all indicators of kidney size in children of group I showed significant differences from those of the CG, with most indicators in group II and some indicators in group III also displaying significant distinctions.

The findings revealed a significant, moderately strong direct correlation between body weight at birth and total plasma protein (TPP) in children of groups I and II, as well as a significant moderately strong direct correlation between gestational age and kidney size. Additionally, there was a significant direct correlation between TPP and the level of serum creatinine clearance (CsS).

A comprehensive evaluation of the general condition of children with very low birth weight (VLBW) and extremely low birth weight (ELBW) across different gestational ages highlighted common clinical symptoms and pathological alterations in vital functions related to cardio-respiratory, urinary, and central nervous system issues.

The primary neurological diagnosis observed in these children was cerebral depression and inhibition alongside severe central nervous system pathology, leading to respiratory dysregulation and suppression of the sucking reflex. This necessitated long-term employment of mechanical ventilation, tube feeding, and infusion feeding in ELBW children.

Premature newborns with Acute Kidney Injury (AKI) posed significant challenges as patients. The rise in creatinine levels after the first week of life, coupled with a swift suppression of diuresis, necessitated the initiation of peritoneal dialysis. However, the overall condition of the patients often prevented the sustained implementation of peritoneal dialysis.

It was concluded that early detection of the initial stages of AKI could be instrumental in preventing fatalities resulting from multiple organ failure. The progression of fluid retention led to cerebral, pulmonary, and peripheral edema, culminating in cardiorespiratory failure and neurological depression. Early intervention to address AKI is crucial in preventing adverse outcomes associated with fluid imbalance and organ dysfunction.

Conclusion. Prematurity has a negative impact on the development of renal tissue in newborns, even though nephrogenesis typically concludes around 36 weeks of gestation. A comprehensive evaluation of children with very low birth weight (VLBW) and extremely low birth weight (ELBW) across different gestational ages highlights the convergence of clinical symptoms and pathological changes in vital functions, stemming from issues related to cardio-respiratory, urinary, and central nervous system functions.

Cystatin C emerges as a dependable marker for eGFR in preterm infants with ELBW and VLBW, offering a sensitivity of 89.5% and 86.7% with specificities of 88.7% and 82.4%, respectively. When combined with an assessment of kidney volume, which provides a specificity of 88.62% and sensitivity of 83.24%, Cystatin C becomes an invaluable tool for evaluating renal function in this particular patient group. This combined approach can enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of assessing renal function in these vulnerable newborns.

REFERENCES

1. Sandokji I, Greenberg JH. Biomarkers for acute kidney injury in children - where are we now? // *Curr Opin Pediatr.* - 2023 - No. 57(1). – p.136-145.
2. Ashurova D. T., Ahmedova D. I. Hormonal adaptation features and neonatal period of newborn children depending on the body weight at birth // *World Healthcare Providers Multidisciplinary medical journal USE.* – 2012. – C. 41-44.
3. White SL, Perkovic V, Cass A, Chang CL. (2019) Is low birth weight an antecedent of CKD in later life? A systematic review of observational studies. // *Am J Kidney Dis*, 2019. - No. 54. – p.248–261.
4. Abitbol CL, Rodriguez MM. The long-term renal and cardiovascular consequences of prematurity. *Nat Rev Nephrol* 2012;28:265-74.